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Stability Analysis and Research of H-Section Cold-Formed Steel Arches

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Abstract: This paper introduced the in-plane and out-of-plane instability numerical analyses of the H-section cold-formed steel arches. To validate the accuracy of the finite element modeling method, the comparison between various finite element methods were conducted. Utilizing the finite element analysis software ABAQUS, eight sets of H-section cold-formed steel arch models with different lateral brace spacing are established. Based on the finite element results, linear and non-linear buckling analyses was performed. The results indicated that the bracing spacing has little influence on the structural stability when in-plane instability is main instability mode for H-section cold formed steel arches. While, when out-of-plane instability is the main instability mode, the larger the bracing spacing of H-section cold formed steel arches is, the worse its structural stability is. It is also shown that wind load often plays a determining role in practical engineering, where inelastic and initial imperfection exists.

Keywords: circular cold-formed steel arch; stability; lateral brace; buckling analysis; finite element analysis.

1. Introduction

The arch is a structural device with curved shape, under the compression in its plane, and with a more reasonable loading condition. It can effectively convert part of the vertical load into the horizontal thrust of its support, and it can also turn the bending moment caused by the external load into the axial force. For its large span, excessive headroom in the building, low cost, short construction period and other advantages, arches in form of curved H-section beams turns out to be common structural forms in some areas.

Roller bending is commonly used in the forming process of arches. Pyramid-type three-roll bending, as shown in Figure 1, is the most common for arches forming among numerous types of

bending. The force is applied by the opposite roll to adjust the distance between the rollers earlier than each pass to successfully bend the component into a smaller radius.

Fig 1. Pyramid roll bending

Guo [1] et.al. conducted the experimental research on the ultimate strength of out-of-plane inelastic buckling of circular steel arches under symmetrical and asymmetric loads. Experimental and finite element analysis results indicated that the initial out-of-plane geometric imperfection, the out-of-plane elastic buckling mode and in-plane loading mode have a significant effect on the out-of-plane inelastic buckling behavior of fixed end steel arches. Pi [2] et al. studied the inelastic buckling behavior and its ultimate strength in the plane of a circular steel arch. Dou[3, 4] et al. investigate the buckling performance and the bearing capacity of elastic-plastic stability of I-shaped arc arches by analyses of eigenvalue and plastic strength.

Based on previous research and practical engineering, this paper used a variety of finite element analysis methods to perform elastic and inelastic buckling analyses of cold-formed steel arches with different lateral brace spacing under real working conditions. The influence of the lateral brace spacing on the inelastic stability of the arch was explored.

2. Project Overview

2.1. Introduction to an actual project

Dry coal shed with a span of 90 meters was built in Lingshi County, Jinzhong District, Shanxi Province. The roof of the coal shed was designed with a solid-web cold-formed steel arch, and the

terrain roughness belongs to Category B. The geometric diagram of the arch calculated in this paper is shown in Figure 2. The arch is a circular arch with a rise-span ratio of 0.28, a span of 90m, the column spacing of 9m, the later braces arrangement. The arch foot is designed as a pin support, the cross section of arch is HN700 × 300 × 13 × 24, and the material of steel is Q345B.

Fig 2. Geometric diagram of arch calculated (Unit: mm)

2.2. Load and load combinations

The load effects include: (1) The gravity load of the structure, which will be automatically calculated by the software; (2) The characteristic value of the permanent load is 1.1kN/m. Considering the tributary areas of the roofing membrane material and later brace, the characteristic value of the permanent load per unit length is calculated to be 0.122kN/m², with the column distance of 9m, the characteristic value of the permanent load is 0.122×9≈1.1kN/m; (3) The characteristic value of the permanent load of roof variable load is 2.7kN/m. According to “load code for the design of building structures”[5,6], it is stipulated that the variable load uniformly distributed on roofs shall not be less than 0.3kN/m² per unit area, and the variable load on the arch roof shall be 0.3 × 9 = 2.7kN/m; (4) The characteristic values of wind load were calculated by the formula $\omega_k = \beta_z \mu_z \omega_0$. According to “Arched steel structure design procedure” [7] JGJ/T249-2011 suggestions For arch steel structures of medium and small span the average wind load multiplied by the wind vibration coefficient can be used to approximate the dynamic wind effect of the structure. The average value of wind vibration coefficient is 1.2~1.8, in this model, and it is safe to choose the wind vibration coefficients as 1.5. The shape factor of wind load μ_s is identified as the “load code for the design of building structures”[5,6], height vibration factor of wind pressure μ_z was also determined according to the load code, The wind reference pressure is taken as $\omega_0=0.45\text{kN/m}^2$.

Load combinations consider the following three basic combinations: (1) permanent load+ full span variable load; (2) permanent load + half span variable load; (3) permanent + wind load.

3. Establishment and comparison of finite element models

To validate the accuracy of the calculation of the overall stability of the solid-web arches, taking 90m span cold-formed solid-web arch (with later brace-spacing of 3.5m, cross section of HN700 × 300 × 13 × 24, and material of Q345B) as an example, where eigenvalue buckling and inelastic buckling analyses were conducted. It uses two kinds of analysis software, Midas and ABAQUS, with 4 different modelling methods discussed, including modeling of Midas single-beam element, modeling of ABAQUS single-shell element, modeling of ABAQUS single beam element and ABAQUS double beam element. By investigating overall stability of cold-formed arches under different loading conditions, the final finite element analysis modeling method were determined.

3.1. Establishment of the finite element model

To better simulate the arch support, in-plane and out-of-plane hinged support was adopted in finite element model, with in-plane and out-of-plane bending moments released but torsion in cross-sectional plane constrained. To simulate the effect of lateral brace applied to the arch, the lateral displacement and axial torsion at the position of lateral brace are restrained. Due to the through arrangement of lateral braces and the existence of gables, out-of-plane support can be considered as a rigid support. The load is applied in the forms of the permanent load, variable load and wind load according to the actual engineering practice. Among them, the wind load was applied in the three loading sections under the local coordinate system, according to the requirements of JGJ/T249-2011 [6].

The modeling process uses different elements as required, material of steel Q345B, poisson's ratio of 0.3, elastic modulus of $E=2.06 \times 10^5 \text{MPa}$, and the material constitutive relationships of the ideal elastoplastic model.

3.2. Analysis results of modeling method of Midas single beam element

In-plane buckling analysis results for the beam-column of Midas Gen are accurate, but out-of-plane buckling analysis results are not ideal. So, it can be used to verify the correctness of the

calculation results corresponding to the in-plane buckling analysis of the ABAQUS model. The modeling procedure of the arch is shown in figure 3. Instability failure of the arch structure will occur when arch subjected permanent load and full-span variable load. In the linear buckling analysis, the first-order buckling mode is shown in figure 4, and its eigenvalue value is 6.856. This result will be used to check the correctness of the ABAQUS model.

Figure 3. Midas modeling results

Figure 4. First-order buckling mode

3.3. Analysis results of modeling method of ABAQUS single shell element

Compared to Midas and ABAQUS beam elements, ABAQUS shell element is a more sophisticated modeling method, which can fully reflect the buckling mechanism of the arch structures. Corresponding, its modeling process is more complex, and the calculation is more time-consuming. So, in this paper, this modeling method is used to verify the calculation results of ABAQUS beam element.

The material used in model was the ideal elastoplastic model. The element type S4R, a four-node shell element with reduced integration and finite membrane strains, was adopted in the finite element analyses. The load is applied according to the actual working conditions. The permanent load and the gravity load are loaded into the first analysis step, static general analysis step. The full-span variable load, half-span variable load or wind load were applied to the second analysis step, arc length analysis step. The buckling analysis step is used for eigenvalue buckling analysis, and the arc length analysis step is used for nonlinear analysis. The analysis results of the modeling of ABAQUS single specimen shell element are summarized as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of modeling and analysis results of ABAQUS single shell element

	Permanent load + full span variable load	Permanent load + Half-span variable load	Permanent load + wind load
Buckling mode	 Out-of Plane		
Buckling eigenvalue	7.48	10.05	9.92
LPF Curve			
LPF Peak	5.70	2.71	4.37

3.4. Analysis results of modeling method of ABAQUS single beam element

Compared with the single shell element, single beam element is a relatively simple way of finite element modeling. Single beam element is calculated to pay more attention to the integrity of the whole component instability, there is no gap between the calculation accuracy of shell and beam elements. And, the finite element analysis results of ABAQUS single beam element is checked and verified by them of ABAQUS single shell element and Midas single beam element. The element type of B32OS was utilized in the model.

The analysis results of ABAQUS single beam element are summarized as shown in Table 2

Table 2. ABAQUS Summary of modeling results of ABAQUS single beam element

	Permanent load + full span variable load	Permanent load + Half-span variable load	Permanent load + wind load
Buckling mode	 Out-of-plane		
Buckling eigenvalue	6.52	7.50	5.46

LPF Peak curve			
LPF Peak	5.09	2.34	3.12

3.5. Analysis results of modeling method of ABAQUS double beam element

To consider the interaction effect between adjacent arch structures, this section establishes a double arch structure with beam elements as the main type of elements. The element types of arch body and secondary beam at both ends adopted B32OS, the element types of diagonal bracing and tie rod adopted B32, and the element type of longitudinal truss adopted T3D2. The cross-section of tie rod 1 is $\varnothing 168 \times 5.0$ round welded pipe; the truss used a combination of square steel pipe 150×4.0 and square steel pipe 70×3.0 ; the diagonal brace uses $\varnothing 159 \times 5.0$ round steel pipe, all of which used the material of Q235. The cross-section of the secondary beam was $HW200 \times 200 \times 8 \times 12$, and the material was Q345. When setting the boundary conditions, the lateral displacement and tangential twist on one side of the arch were constrained. Figure 5 is the schematic diagram of double beam element model.

The analysis results of the ABAQUS double beam element modeling are summarized in Table 3.

Figure 5. ABAQUS Modeling of ABAQUS double beam element

Table 3. Summary of modeling results of ABAQUS double beam element

	Dead load + full span live load	Dead load + Half-span live load	Constant load + wind load
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Buckling mode	 Out-of-plane		
Buckling eigenvalue	7.02	6.45	5.28
LPF Peak curve			
LPF Peak	5.36	2.57	3.51

3.6. Comparison of results from different modeling methods

The finite element analysis results of four modeling are summarized, as shown in Table 4. After comparison, considering the time cost, calculation accuracy, and reliability considerations, it was decided to use ABAQUS software to build a model of the single beam element for further calculation, with the effects of geometric inelastic and initial imperfections be considered.

Table 4. Summary of the results of different modeling methods

Modeling approach	Full span live load		Half-span live load		Wind load	
	Buckling eigenvalue	LPF Peak	Buckling eigenvalue	LPF Peak	Buckling eigenvalue	LPF peak
Midas Single beam element	6.86					
ABAQUS Single shell unit	7.48	5.70	10.05	2.70	9.92	4.37
ABAQUS single beam element	6.52	5.09	7.50	2.34	5.46	3.12
ABAQUS double beam element	7.02	5.36	6.45	2.57	5.28	3.51

Table 3. Summary of ABAQUS calculation results

Support distance	Dead load + full span live load			Dead load + semi-span live load			Constant load + wind load		
	Buckling Modal	Buckling Eigenvalues	LPF Peak	Buckling Modal	Buckling Eigenvalues	LPF Peak	Buckling Modal	Buckling Eigenvalues	LPF Peak
2m	In-plane	7.74	5.46	In-plane	14.91	3.24	Out-of Plane	18.72	2.86
3m	In-plane	7.74	6.02	In-plane	15.32	3.28	Out-of Plane	9.05	2.71
4m	In-plane	7.74	6.02	In-plane	11.09	2.85	Out-of Plane	5.22	2.63
5m	In-plane	7.74	6.01	In-plane	8.07	3.02	Out-of Plane	4.29	2.9
6m	In-plane	7.74	6.01	Out-of Plane	5.64	2.76	Out-of Plane	3.18	2.71
7m	In-plane	7.74	6.01	Out-of Plane	4.23	2.49	Out-of Plane	1.91	1.78
8m	In-plane	7.74	6.01	Out-of Plane	3.32	2.24	Out-of Plane	1.82	1.42
9m	Out-of Plane	4.44	3.47	Out-of Plane	1.67	1.61	Out-of Plane	0.90	0.66

4. Effect of support spacing on arch stability

To investigate the influence of the support spacing on the stability of the arch, the stability calculations of the arches with different support spacings of the structure, as mentioned above, were performed. The parameter is set to the lateral support distance of the arch, which is set to 2m,

3m, 4m, 5m, 6m, 7m, 8m, 9m, covering most of the possible range of the 90m span arch support distance of the column distance of 9m .

4.1. Summary of finite element analysis results

For arches with support distances of 2m, 3m, 4m, 5m, 6m, 7m, 8m, and 9m, the eigenvalue buckling analysis and arc-length method nonlinear analysis under three basic combinations are performed to obtain the buckling modes and buckling characteristics. The analysis results of the values and peaks of LPF are shown in Table 5. The calculation results of the finite element are analyzed below to discuss the influence of the out-of-plane support spacing on the out-of-plane stability of the arch.

4.2. Eigenvalue buckling analysis

The results of the eigenvalue buckling analysis are compared laterally, and the comparison results are shown in Figure 6.

In the eigenvalue buckling analysis, the change of the out-of-plane support spacing has no effect on the arch under constant load and full-span live load. The first-order buckling eigenvalue of the structure is 7.74, which is an ideal situation without initial defects. The first-order buckling load of the structure is double the dead load and self-weight, and the superimposed. 7.74 times live load is $7.74 \times 2.7\text{kN} / \text{m} = 20.898\text{kN} / \text{m}$ line load.

Figure 6. Comparison of buckling eigenvalues at different support distances

For constant load and semi-span live load, in-plane buckling occurs at a support distance of 2m; out-of-plane buckling occurs at 3m to 6m, and as the out-of-plane support distance increases, the

characteristic value of buckling decreases.

For the constant load + wind load, the buckling eigenvalues of the previous steps are all negative, which means that the wind load will only occur when the wind load is reversely applied. It is a definite order, which is listed in the table, and all the out-of-plane instabilities occur. As the out-of-plane support distance becomes larger, the buckling characteristic value becomes smaller.

4.3. Nonlinear buckling analysis

The nonlinear buckling analysis of the structure uses the arc-length method. The arc length method solves the arc length-LPF curve. LPF (Load Proportionality Factor) is the specified multiple to which the load is applied. The peak LPF is the maximum load multiple that the structure can withstand. It reflects the ultimate bearing capacity of the structure considering the bi-linear and initial defects.

The most probable instability mode is obtained through the linear buckling analysis in the previous step. According to the design proposal of the specification, the arch axis length is 1/1000 as the maximum geometric initial defect when the instability is in the arch plane. For the 1 / 500th of the longest arch axis length between the lateral supports as the maximum value of the initial geometric defect, a nonlinear model is introduced and calculated by the arc length method to obtain the final safety factor and LPF peak.

The results of the eigenvalue buckling analysis are compared laterally, and the comparison results are shown in FIG. 7.

Figure 7. Comparison of LPF peaks at different support spacings

In the non-linear analysis of the arc length method, it can be seen that under constant load and full-span live load, the LPF peak value is 6.0 when the support distance is 2m to 8m, indicating that it

is not affected by the out-of-plane support distance, and When the support distance is 9m, the peak value of LPF drops directly to 3.47 as the instability mode becomes out-of-plane instability.

Under constant load + semi-span live load and constant load + wind load, the peak LPF of the structure decreases with the increase of the out-of-plane support distance.

5. Conclusion

1) In the eigenvalue buckling analysis, when the support distance is small, in-plane instability caused by constant load + full-span live load is the controlling factor. As the support distance exceeds 3m, the wind load starts to control, and with the surface as the distance between the outer supports becomes larger, the buckling characteristic value becomes smaller and smaller.

2) In the non-linear analysis, the constant load + full span live load is not affected from 2m to 8m, and the buckling mode changes from in-plane instability to out-of-plane instability when the length exceeds 8m, and the peak value of LPF decreases. Under constant load + semi-span live load and constant load + wind load, the peak LPF of the structure decreases with the increase of the out-of-plane support distance. And wind load always plays a controlling role in nonlinear analysis.

3) When the effective first-order instability mode is in-plane instability (under constant load of 2m to 8m + full span live load case, under constant load of 2m to 3m + half span live load case), it can be found that the support spacing has a small effect on its stability. When the effective first-order instability mode is out-of-plane instability, it can be seen that the support spacing has a greater impact on stability. The main trend is that the greater the support spacing, the more likely it is that out-of-plane instability occurs.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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